

Structural, Raman spectroscopy and FTIR Analysis of $Zn_{0.9}Sr_{0.1}Bi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ Ceramic material

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals $Zn_{0.9}Sr_{0.1}Bi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ (ZSBT) of four-layer Aurivillius compound synthesised by Solid-State Reaction (SSR) method. The sample is calcinated at 950°C for 4 hrs and sintered at 1100 °C for 2 hrs. The sample has orthorhombic crystal structure which is found by XRD and is confirmed the same by the Raman spectroscopy. The microstructure is recognised as plate-like grains and their measurements are also done by SEM. Different elements present in the sample are estimated by EDS. Phonon modes of this compound are studied at around ~118, ~231, ~268, ~535, and 849 cm^{-1} by Raman spectroscopy. Vibrational modes of ZSBT are studied by FTIR spectrum.

Keywords: Solid-State Reaction method, X-Ray Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscope, Raman spectroscopy and FTIR.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bismuth Layered-Structure Ferroelectrics (BLSF) compounds are belongs to Aurivillius Structure (AS) group, AS was invented by Bengt Aurivillius in 1949 [1 - 3]. He was suggested a formula as $[Bi_2O_2]^{2+} [A_{m-1}B_mO_{3m+1}]^{2-}$ or $A_{m-1}Bi_2B_mO_{3m+3}$, here $m = 1$ to 5 and more, it shows no. of perovskite layers lies in middle of the $[Bi_2O_2]^{2+}$ layers. Where A is a large radii cations (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , and lanthanides Ln^{3+}), and B is a smaller radii cations (Cr^{3+} , Ga^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Mn^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , Nb^{5+} , and W^{6+}). The crystal structure of present compound is AS related to $m = 4$. The AS materials are utilized in various areas of experimental applications to be non-volatile ferroelectric random access memory (FeRAM), ionic conductors, catalytic materials, electroluminescent thin films, and multiferroics [4 – 9]. Four-layer AS along $m = 4$ like $BaBi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ (BBT), $CaBi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ (CBT), and $SrBi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ (SBT) indicates elevated switching limits at low operating voltage, it is essential for manufacturing of FeRAM [10 – 15].

The utility of A-site interchange is highly clear than that of B-site replacement, because the B-sites are indistinguishable in size and do not shows a main structural effect in the polarization process as BLSFs. Now a days the major part of A-site cations shows in explanation of structural analysis in the ferroelectric behaviour of this compound [16]. $Zn_{0.9}Sr_{0.1}Bi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ (ZSBT) is one of the AS of BLSF group owing to $m = 4$, the structure of ZSBT is orthorhombic replicate part of perovskite layers along modifying $[Bi_2O_2]^{2+}$ layers by the c-axis [17 – 19].

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

ZSBT is synthesised by Solid-State Reaction (SSR) method with high purity (99.9%) of ZnO, SrO ($SrCO_3$), Bi_2O_3 , TiO_2 are the raw chemicals, which are mixing of stoichiometric ratio. The SSR process builds upon physical quantities and modify with the reaction [20, 21]. In this method the first step is weighing different oxides/carbonates using an electrical balance. The weighed and mixed chemical powders were taken into Teflon jars of ball miller (Retsch PM-400, Germany) and grinded at 300 rpm for 10 hours in the presence of acetone medium. The blended compound is heated at 70 °C in a hot air oven; at last the slurry is calcinated at 950 °C for 4 hours in an alumina crucible and placed it in an Electronic Silicon Carbide Programmable (ESCP) Furnace. The temperature changes from 30 °C to 950 °C (~ 10 °C per minute). Again the mixtures of raw powders are grinded for 10 hours with zirconia balls 1:10 ratio, the binder PVA of 2% added to calcinated powder. Finally pellets are made by the powder inserted into circular and cylindrical compact disk, pressed into size of 0.2 cm thickness and 1cm diameter at 8 tons. Using ESCP furnace sintered the pellets at 1100°C according to a heating rate of 5 °C/min for 2 hours.

The structure of ZSBT crystal is measured by an X-ray diffractometer using CuK_α radiation in the range of $2\theta = 10$ to 70° with step dimension of 0.02° . The surface morphology and elemental identification of ZSBT is studied by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) combined with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Raman scattering analysis is measured by a Raman spectrometer with 514.5 nm excitation line of an argon laser source. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) examined in the range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} .

III. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The XRD information of the $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{15}$ (ZSBT) was shown in figure (1) and confirmed as an orthorhombic phase with space group of $A2_1am$ and compared with JCPDS File No 43-0973. There were no secondary phases identified in this compound, which suggests that the replace of Zn^{2+} cations enter into the B-site of pseudo-perovskite and forms a solid solution. The most intensive peak refers to the (119) plane, which was consistent with the BLSFs of the type of (11 2 m +1) [22]. XRD data certify the BLSF structure with $m = 4$. By using the CHEKCELL software within the error limit of $\pm 0.002\text{ \AA}$, lattice constants were measured as $a=5.410\text{ \AA}$, $b=5.435\text{ \AA}$ and $c=42.14\text{ \AA}$, Volume (V)= 1239.28 (\AA)^3 . Therefore the orthorhombic distortion is calculated by the formula $2(a-b)/(a+b)$ and it is equal to 0.0044. The density of the ZSBT ceramic was measured via the Archimedes method is 97.2%.

Figure 1: XRD peaks of $\text{Zn}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Bi}_4\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{15}$

The structural morphology of ZSBT is shown in figure (2), from this it is clear that the compact structure of ZSBT is due to its BLSFs characteristics. The shapes of the grains are plate-like with an anisotropic nature and they comprise magnifying feature of compound. The average grain sizes of prepared ceramic are $\sim 1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The grain growth increases along a-b plane when compared to c-axis. The microstructure of grain size leads to increase the ferroelectric behavior of the materials.

Figure 2: SEM images of ZSBT

The Elemental analysis of the compound is estimated by EDS, its coloured dot mappings and spectrum are shown in figure (3). The atomic percentage of Zn, Sr, Bi, Ti, and O elements to be 4.76%, 1.84%, 57.61%, 15.21%, and 26.62%. The elemental mapping for ZSBT ceramic is homogeneous with a slight variation in the stoichiometry may be due to Bi volatilization and loss at the high-temperature sintering process.

Figure 3: (a) All the atoms in ZSBT ceramic, (b) Zn (c) Sr, (d) Bi, (e) Ti, (f) O elements, and (g) Energy dispersive spectrum.

Raman spectroscopy studied at room temperature, the spectra of ZSBT ceramic is shown in figure (4). Sharp phonon modes of this compound are observed at around ~ 118 , ~ 231 , ~ 268 , ~ 535 , and 849 cm^{-1} . The less frequency modes are associated with the motion of heavy Bi^{3+} ions, which is allotted to vibrations of “Rigid layers” and is commonly identified in layered structures [23]. In these modes, at $\sim 118 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicated to translational modes of Bi and Ti sites, at $\sim 231 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is specified to TiO_6 bending and tilting modes. The band below 200 cm^{-1} is related to vibrations between Bi and O atoms [24] and above this mode corresponds to A_{1g} character of TiO_6 octahedra. At ~ 268 shows B_{2g} and B_{3g} modes are correlated to O-Ti-O bending vibrations, at $\sim 535 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates to A_{1g} mode opposing excursion of Oxygen atom of TiO_6 octahedra. The peak $\sim 849 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was reported to B_{1g} mode which represents the symmetric stretching of TiO_6 [25]. Raman results are in agreement with the XRD data, indicating an ordered of orthorhombic structure with $A2_1am$ space group at short and long distances.

Figure 4: Raman spectra of ZSBT sample

Fourier transforms infrared (FTIR) spectra of ZSBT compound is presented in figure (5), in these peaks the weak absorption band indicates at 462.13 cm^{-1} which correspond to Ti-O bending vibration. The ceramic exhibit a main transmission band at 528.5 cm^{-1} attributed to stretching vibrations of Ti-O octahedral. At 815.89 cm^{-1} is assigned to the vibrations from strongly covalently bonded $(\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3)^{2+}$ layers [26, 27] belong to Bi-O and Ti-O stretching vibrations respectively. O-H group of less intense peak occur at 1460.11 cm^{-1} and existence of the peak may be bending bonds.

Figure-5: FTIR bands of ZSBT compound

CONCLUSION

The ferroelectric compound of $Zn_{0.9}Sr_{0.1}Bi_4Ti_4O_{15}$ is prepared by Solid-state reaction process utilising ball milling for 10 hrs. The sample is calcinated at $950\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and sintered at $1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. XRD data concluded a single phase orthorhombic structure in perovskite site with $A2_1am$ space group. SEM images finalised a plate-like grains randomly oriented in this material, it appeared anisotropic four-layered structure. Various phonon modes are explained through Raman spectroscopy and decided the crystal structure is orthorhombic. The distinct vibration bands of ZSBT ceramic is reported by Fourier transform Infrared spectrometer.

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